

insect and the stage when it feeds on plants.

Results of rearing are presented in the table. The average number of adults collected per month was 4,402 in 1975,

6,540 in 1976, 18,912 in 1977, and 24,594 in 1978. The insects are useful for continuity in mass rearing, varietal screening, and other gall midge experiments. ■

Agriculture). IR30, and OS6 — were compared at 4 rates of N (0, 150, 300, and 450 ppm), replicated 3 times in 10-liter plastic pots that were watered once daily, without flooding. Data on soil water-holding capacity were not collected. Soil analysis before cropping indicated a pH of 6.7, 2.2% organic C, 0.17% total N, 6.7 kg available P/ha, and 238 kg available K/ha.

IR30 had the highest mean harvest Index (86.7%) and differed highly significantly from the other rices ($P < 0.01$) (see table). That implies that IR30 used a greater proportion of the nutrients in the production of grain than of straw. The other cultivars did not differ significantly. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Drought resistance

Screening for harvest index in upland rice in southwestern Nigeria

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Yields of rainfed upland rice are low in the rain forest zone of southwestern Nigeria partly because farmers use OS6, a long-culmed, low-tillering, and lodging-susceptible cultivar that responds poorly to fertilizer nitrogen (N). Lodging adversely affects percentage of filled grains, a major yield component.

The selection criteria suggested for high-yielding, N-responsive semidwarf cultivars include harvest index, ratio of

grain, and biological yield (excluding root weight).

Among the rice accessions screened in the greenhouse, 5 improved cultivars—TOS4164, TOS4172, TOS4632 (from the International Institute of Tropical

Harvest indexes of 5 rice cultivars.^a University of Ife, Ibadan, Nigeria.

Cultivars	Harvest index (%)				Mean
	0 ppm N	150 ppm N	300 ppm N	450 ppm N	
IR30	99.9	115.7	51.3	74.0	86.7 a
TOS4164	75.5	49.3	46.8	64.4	59.0 b
TOS4172	52.0	58.8	62.8	47.0	55.2 b
TOS4632	60.4	55.0	42.5	45.5	50.9 b
OS6	48.7	56.9	63.7	64.4	58.4 b

^a Standard error = 13.0. Coefficient of variation = 21.0%. Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Adverse soils tolerance

IR42: a modern variety suited to the small rice farmer

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Small farmers lack the resources to provide the water control and management inputs needed to extract the high yield potential of modern varieties. To benefit from the green revolution, they need varieties with built-in tolerance for adverse environmental factors, i.e., too little or too much water, diseases and insects, and nutrient deficiencies and soil toxicities. The Philippine-named IR42 is the closest we have to such a variety.

IR42 has good agronomic characteristics. It yields well at low levels of nitrogen and phosphorus

fertilizers and has moderate tolerance for salinity, alkalinity, iron toxicity, excess organic matter, and zinc deficiency. It is resistant to rice tungro

virus, grassy stunt, bacterial blight and blast, and has intermediate resistance to sheath blight and *Cercospora* leaf spot. It has resistance to biotypes 1 and 2 of

Performance of IR42 and of other IR varieties on 6 problem soils. Philippines, 1978 dry and wet seasons.

Problem	Variety	Rating ^a	Grain yield (t/ha)	Location
Salinity	IR42	MT	5.6	Sinacaban, Misamis Occidental
	IR4630-22	T	5.1	
Iron toxicity	IR42	MT	4.6	Malinao, Camarines Sur
	IR36	T	2.2	
Peat soil	IR42	MT	4.2	Colorado, Agusan del Norte
	IR34	T	2.4	
Nitrogen deficiency	IR42	—	4.6	IRRI
	IR34	—	1.2	
Phosphorus deficiency	IR42	MT	3.9	Pangil, Laguna
	IR20	T	4.2	
Zinc deficiency ^b	IR42	MT	5.4	Gen. Santos, South Cotabato
	IR34	T	5.0	

^aMT = moderately tolerant, T = tolerant. ^bPartly corrected by zinc oxide dip.